

Unravelling sodium-ion transport, kinetic properties and ageing mechanisms in Mn-rich $\text{Na}_{3.4}\text{Mn}_{1.2}\text{Ti}_{0.8}(\text{PO}_4)_3/\text{C}$ NASICON cathode

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Na-ion battery
Cathode materials
Mn-based NASICON
Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy
Distribution of relaxation times

ABSTRACT

Among the cathode materials of the formula $\text{Na}_{3+2x}\text{Mn}_{1+x}\text{Ti}_{1-x}(\text{PO}_4)_3$, the compound with $x = 0.2$ represent the best trade-off between electrochemical performances and phase purity. However, this material still suffers from important shortcomings, such as voltage hysteresis, incomplete utilization of manganese redox processes and unclear ageing mechanisms. Herein, we conduct an extensive electrochemical investigation of the $\text{Na}_{3.4}\text{Mn}_{1.2}\text{Ti}_{0.8}(\text{PO}_4)_3/\text{C}$ cathode, with particular emphasis on the interplay between structure, Na^+ transport, and reaction kinetics, trying also to clarify their role in determining the capacity fade. The effects of kinetic polarization are clearly visible in rate capability test, where redox peaks are shifted beyond the operational voltage window, inhibiting the $\text{Mn}^{4+}/\text{Mn}^{3+}$ and $\text{Ti}^{4+}/\text{Ti}^{3+}$ redox couples, and practically limiting the accessible capacity at high current densities. However, the kinetic polarization cannot explain the voltage hysteresis and the gap between practical and theoretical Na^+ extracted/inserted encountered during the near-equilibrium condition GITT measurements. Therefore, these limitations can be also attributed to intrinsic structural factors, such as the anti-site disorder originated from manganese dislocation in Na vacancies. Finally, the ageing mechanism have been investigated through long-term EIS and GITT analysis, demonstrating that the capacity fade encountered for Mn-based NASICON cathodes is predominantly governed by a progressive slowdown of solid-state Na^+ diffusion rather than interfacial degradation and charge-transfer limitations, with no structural transformations and electrode deterioration after 1500 cycles confirmed by post-mortem analysis. Overall, the obtained results provide a comprehensive understanding of electrochemical properties and degradation mechanisms in Mn-rich NASICON cathodes, thus paving the way to further improvements on electrochemical performances of phosphate-based cathodes for sodium-ion battery.

1. Introduction

The growing demand for sustainable and cost-effective energy storage technologies has triggered extensive research into attractive alternatives to the well-established lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) [1]. Owing to the natural abundance and wide global distribution of Na resources, sodium-ion batteries (SIBs) are attracting great attention as low-cost and sustainable complementary technology with respect to LIBs [2]. In particular, SIBs are expected to be the more appealing device for large-scale stationary energy storage system [3]. Nonetheless, the development of high-performance electrode materials can broaden the extensive penetration of SIBs in other sectors such as mobility and portable electronics. In particular, the research is focused on the

cathodic materials since they represents the key component limiting the performance of the battery [4]. However, the development of high-performance cathode materials remains a critical challenge, as sodium ions possess a larger ionic radius than lithium ions, which often leads to sluggish diffusion kinetics and structural instability during cycling [5]. There are different types of cathode materials currently under investigation, such as Transition Metal Oxides, Polyanionic Compounds and Prussian Blue Analogues, each with its own advantages and limitations [6]. Among the various candidates, polyanionic compounds based on the NASICON (Na^+ SuperIonic CONductor) structure, and in particular the NASICON-phosphates, have emerged as particularly attractive, mainly due to their long-term structural stability and high ionic conductivity [7,8]. Indeed, they are characterized by a robust

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2026.149011>

Received 27 February 2026; Received in revised form 24 April 2026; Accepted 3 May 2026

Available online 3 May 2026

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3D open framework made of corner-sharing transition metal oxides (TMO₆) octahedra and PO₄ tetrahedra, [9] which provides large diffusion channels for fast Na⁺ transport. Moreover, the strong covalent character of P-O bond improves the stability of the oxygen in the lattice, thus increasing the safety of the material. On the other hand, the ionicity of the TM-O bond is promoted, thus enhancing the redox potential of the system through the so-called “inductive effect” [10,11].

Within this family, the Vanadium-based NASICON compounds, such as the well-known Na₃V₂(PO₄)₃, are the most representative and investigated NASICON-structured cathodes. However, the toxicity and environmental concerns of vanadium have driven the exploration of new NASICON-type cathodes based on abundant and eco-friendly metals such as manganese and iron [9]. In particular, Mn-based NASICON cathode materials have drawn considerable attention since they can combine the economic and environmental sustainability with the high energy density associated with the slightly higher operating voltage plateau of Mn³⁺/Mn²⁺ redox couple compared to V⁴⁺/V³⁺ [12]. Moreover, when manganese is partially substituted with another TM, multiple electron transfers can be achieved, thus unlocking the high operating voltage Mn⁴⁺/Mn³⁺ redox couple vs Na⁺/Na [13]. In addition, when Mn is substituted with appropriate metals, the typical Jahn-Teller distortion effect of Mn³⁺(3d⁴, high spin) can be strongly mitigated, thus leading to improved cycling stability [14]. Recent efforts have therefore focused on optimizing Mn-based NASICON cathodes by single heteroatom doping/substitution, such as those proposed with Cr [15], Ti [16] and Zr [17], where Ti⁴⁺ have received paramount attention since it allows a reversible three electron reaction in the potential window 1.5 – 4.3 V vs Na⁺/Na. However, the third electron transfer involving the Ti⁴⁺/Ti³⁺ couple occurs at low-voltage (~ 2.10 - 2.20 V vs Na⁺/Na), thus being practically inaccessible in typical full cell configuration [18]. Moreover, this reaction can be only activated in half cell configuration during the second discharge process, thus limiting the amount of extractable Na⁺ at the first desodiation. A common strategy to limit this issue is to maximize the Mn²⁺ content in the crystal lattice at the expense of Ti⁴⁺. However, it has been proven that increasing the Mn content leads to the increasing of Jahn-Teller-driven lattice distortion, the formation of impurity phases, [13] and inherently the promotion of the site hopping of Mn²⁺ to the Na⁺ vacancies which deteriorate the performance of the materials [18]. The latter shortcoming, known as intrinsic anti-site defect (IASD), has been reported as the main source of typical voltage hysteresis and capacity loss encountered in Mn-based NASICON [19]. In this context, extensive research have been devoted to reduce the IASD-related implications through different strategies, such as cation doping, [9,20,21] anion substitution, [22] and sodium excess to fill Na⁺ vacancies for Mn²⁺ occupation [18,23–25]. The latter approach is particularly attractive since do not require additional elements, keeping the material cost and synthesis steady. Recent studies found that the compound Na_{3.4}Mn_{1.2}Ti_{0.8}(PO₄)₃ represent the best stoichiometry as trade-off between electrochemical performances and phase purity [13,26]. However, to the best of our knowledge, a deep and comprehensive electrochemical characterization of the Mn-rich phase Na_{3.4}Mn_{1.2}Ti_{0.8}(PO₄)₃ NASICON cathode is still missing, hindering the full understanding of its sodium storage behavior. In particular, beyond capacity and rate performance, the main sources of polarization and incomplete utilization of redox centers, as well as the role of solid-state Na⁺ diffusion and interfacial charge-transfer processes, must be carefully investigated, since they largely determine the electrochemical behavior and durability of Mn-rich NASICON cathodes. However, despite the increasing number of reports on Mn-based NASICON materials, [27] detailed electrochemical analysis remain limited. Moreover, the mechanism responsible of capacity fade of Mn-rich NASICON-type materials is still unclear [19]. In this context, the use of advanced electrochemical techniques such as cyclic voltammetry at variable scan rates, galvanostatic intermittent titration technique (GITT) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) provide plenty of information about interfacial processes and Na⁺ transport. Furthermore, the

application of distribution of relaxation times (DRT) analysis to EIS data enables the deconvolution of overlapping electrochemical processes, allowing a clearer identification of their contribution to the polarization at different state of charge [28]. Herein, we synthesize and perform a deep electrochemical characterization of Na_{3.4}Mn_{1.2}Ti_{0.8}(PO₄)₃/C, focusing the attention on the investigation of the sodium ion transport properties, reaction kinetics and interfacial properties, as well as their role in determining long-term cycling stability. By combining galvanostatic cycling with CV, GITT, EIS and DRT analyses, we aim to establish clear correlations between kinetic processes and electrochemical performance, providing fundamental insights into the aging mechanisms of Mn-rich NASICON cathodes and helping the rational design of durable sodium-ion battery materials.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Material synthesis

Na_{3.4}Mn_{1.2}Ti_{0.8}(PO₄)₃/C (here named as NM_{1.2}TP/C) was prepared by a simple sol-gel method using stoichiometric amount of sodium acetate (≥ 99.0 %, Sigma Aldrich), manganese acetate tetrahydrate (≥ 99.0 %, Sigma Aldrich), titanium (IV) bis(ammonium lactato)dihydroxide (50 % wt. in H₂O, Sigma Aldrich) and ammonium dihydrogen phosphate (99.99 %, Sigma Aldrich). All the precursors were dissolved in distilled water at room temperature for 1 h. Then, citric acid was added to the solutions and left stirring at 80 °C in oil bath until gels are formed. The gel was collected and further dried overnight at 120 °C in an oven. The obtained sample was heated at 650 °C at 5 °C min⁻¹ for 10 h in a tubular furnace under constant Argon flow. After cooling down, the sample was ground to obtain a fine powder.

2.2. Material characterizations and ex-situ measurements

Carbon content in the cathode sample was estimated by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) using a Perkin-Elmer STA 6000 Thermal Analyzer. The air flow rate was set to 50 mL min⁻¹ and an alumina crucible was used to hold the sample. After equilibration, the powder was heated up to 750 °C at a rate of 10 °C min⁻¹. The crystal structure of the cathode powder, pristine and cycled electrodes were investigated by X-ray diffraction (XRD), using a Bruker D6 Phaser (40 kV, 15 mA) with non-monochromated Cu-Kα radiation (λ = 1.5406 Å) equipped with a Si-strip SSD160–2 detector with 160 channels. Scans were performed in Bragg-Brentano mode in the 2θ range 10–80° at a rate of 2.00 s step⁻¹ and a step size of 0.02°. Rietveld refinement of the XRD pattern was carried out through the MAUD software [29] by using the reference parameters of Na₃MnTi(PO₄)₃ (R-3c space group, N. 167, ICSD #253083) [16]. The atomic displacement parameters have been forced to have the same values for Mn, Ti, Na and (PO₄)³⁻ anions. The weighted-profile R factor (R_{wp}%) value was <6. Raman spectroscopy was performed using an Horiba IHR 320 instrument with a laser wavelength of 532 nm. The morphology of the cathode material and the mapping of the elements were assessed by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Energy Dispersive X ray analysis (EDX) using a ZEISS EVO - 10 equipped with explore 30 EDX detector. Elemental compositional analysis was determined with an ICP-OES (ThermoScientific iCAP PRO) and EDX analysis. The morphologies of pristine and cycled electrodes were performed using a FE-SEM ZEISS Sigma 300. Prior the analysis, the cycled electrodes were washed three times with dimethyl carbonate.

2.3. Electrodes preparation and cells assembly

Cathodes were made by mixing the active material, Super-P carbon (Imerys) conductive agent, and polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) binder (Solef Solvay) in the ratio 85:10:5 w/w. Slurry was dispersed in N-methylpyrrolidone (Sigma Aldrich) and coated onto Al foil using the

doctor blade technique (wet thickness of coating = 150 μm). The layers were left to dry at 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Circular electrodes (9-mm diameter) were cut and densified with a hydraulic press (Perkin-Elmer) for 30 s at 6.3 ton cm^{-2} and further dried at 120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ under vacuum for 12 h using a Buchi vacuum oven. The loadings of active materials were in the range 2.2–3.0 mg cm^{-2} for all the electrodes. Na half-cells were prepared by assembling three-electrode Swagelok-type cells in an argon-filled glove box (Jacomex GP-campus, oxygen and moisture content <0.8 ppm) using NASICON cathode as working electrode and metallic sodium as reference and counter electrodes. Only for staircase potentiometric impedance spectroscopy experiment an ECC-Std cell (EL-Cell $\text{\textcircled{R}}$) using a sodium metal ring as a reference electrode and sodium metal disk as a counter electrode was used. For all experiments, a 1 M solution of NaPF_6 (Sigma-Aldrich) in ethylene carbonate (EC)/ propylene carbonate (PC) (1:1 in volume) (Sigma-Aldrich) with 2 % fluoroethylenecarbonate (FEC) additive was used as the electrolyte and 12 mm glass fiber disks (Whatman GF/D) as separator.

2.4. Electrochemical measurement

All electrochemical tests were carried out using a VMP-2Z multi-channel electrochemical workstation by Bio-Logic in the potential window $1.5 < E_{\text{we}} < 4.2 \text{ V}$ vs Na^+/Na . Cyclic voltammeteries (CVs) in Na half-cells were performed at different scanning rates ranging from 0.10 mV s^{-1} to 0.30 mV s^{-1} . Charge/discharge performance of the $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP}/\text{C}$

C electrode were evaluated performing a galvanostatic cycling with a constant current of 500 mA g^{-1} calculated with respect to active material mass. For the sake of clarity, in this work the active material mass takes into account both $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP}$ and C weight contributions, since carbon plays an active role in enhancing the electronic conductivity of the composite material. $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP}/\text{C}$ rate capability was evaluated in the 50–2000 mA g^{-1} current range (5 cycles at every rate), where the overall $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP}/\text{C}$ mass is thus considered for the estimation of specific current and capacity. Galvanostatic Intermittent Titration Technique (GITT) was used to estimate the diffusion coefficient of $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP}/\text{C}$ cathode material during charge and discharge, applying a current pulse of 10 mA g^{-1} for 0.5 h followed by 2 h of relaxation to ensure that the cell reaches the near-equilibrium condition. To deeply understand the kinetic properties as well as the interfacial and the sodium storage behaviors of $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP}/\text{C}$ electrodes, staircase potential-controlled impedance spectroscopy (SPEIS) was carried out during desodiation and sodiation at different State of Charge (SoC). The impedance measurements were carried out at 10th cycle applying an AC pulse of 10 mV amplitude in the frequency range $15 \text{ kHz} \geq f \geq 50 \text{ mHz}$. Additionally, to investigate the evolution of the above-mentioned properties and ageing phenomena occurring in $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP}/\text{C}$ electrodes, EIS analysis was carried out upon prolonged cycling using a three-electrode Swagelok-type T-cell, performing measurements at the second cycle and each tenth cycle until 90 cycles, and each hundredth cycles until 1500 cycles. The spectra were acquired at a bias potential of $E_{\text{we}} = 2.9 \text{ V}$ vs Na^+/Na applying an AC

Fig. 1. a) XRD patterns of synthesized $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP}/\text{C}$ compared to reference diffractogram of $\text{Na}_3\text{MnTi}(\text{PO}_4)_3$ (ICSD #253083); b) Schematic illustration of $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP}$ crystal structure; c) TGA of $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP}/\text{C}$; d) Raman spectrum of $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP}/\text{C}$ powder.

voltage perturbation of 10 mV in the frequency range $15 \text{ kHz} \geq f \geq 50 \text{ mHz}$.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Structural and morphological characterization of the synthesized $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP/C}$

The XRD diffraction pattern of the synthesized $\text{Na}_{3.4}\text{Mn}_{1.2}\text{Ti}_{0.8}(\text{PO}_4)_3/\text{C}$ indicates that the materials crystallized in the rhombohedral NASICON-type unit cell with R-3c space group (Fig. 1a). The crystal structure comprises corner-sharing TMO_6 octahedra (TM = Mn and Ti) and PO_4 tetrahedra as shown in Fig. 1b. In this framework, two types of interstitial sites are available for Na^+ ions, named Na1 and Na2, corresponding to six- and eight- coordination numbers, respectively [15]. The Rietveld refinement depicted in Fig. S1 demonstrate a high level of convergence between experimental and refined data with $R_{\text{wp}}\%$ of ~ 4.42 [30]. The lattice parameters were estimated to be $a = b = 8.93 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 22.24 \text{ \AA}$ with an expansion of the lattice respect to the reference crystal $\text{Na}_3\text{MnTi}(\text{PO}_4)_3$ ascribed to the partial replacement of the smaller Ti^{4+} (0.60 \AA) with the larger Mn^{2+} (0.83 \AA) as well as to the addition of extra Na^+ . As expected, the cell volume moves from 1464.13 to 1534.50 \AA^3 (Table S1) for $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP/C}$. This expansion is also reflected by the c/a ratio, indicating the trigonal distortion of the lattice, which is slightly higher in the $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP/C}$ with respect to the reference, but close to the ideal one (2.449), due to the already described higher Mn^{2+} amount which promotes the positive elongation along c [16]. The estimation of the amount of Mn dislocated in Na vacancies has been performed allowing the concurrent occupation of Mn^{2+} in Na1 and Na2 sites during Rietveld refinement. According to the site occupancy results (Fig. S1 and Table S1), the concentration of Mn/Na IASDs is around 3.67 %, slightly below values reported in literature for $\text{Na}_3\text{MnTi}(\text{PO}_4)_3$ [19,23]. This divergence can be related to the higher amount of sodium in $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP/C}$ cathode, which reduce the amount of vacancies available for Mn occupation. To estimate the amount of carbon in the $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP/C}$ material, TGA analysis was performed as shown in Fig. 1c. According to that, the citric acid decomposition during the annealing lead to a carbon content of around 22.4 %. Although the amount of carbon could be considered quite high respect to other Mn-based NASICON materials found in literature, [9,13,15,26] herein less amount of conductive carbon has been used during electrodes fabrication (10 %) against the 20 % of the herein mentioned works. Nonetheless, although such elevated carbon fractions either as additive in the electrode or as coating obtained during synthesis play a beneficial role in enhancing the electronic conductivity of the composite, thereby improving rate capability performances and reducing polarization during cycling, this comes at the expense of a reduced tap density and, consequently, lower volumetric energy density [31]. In addition, the presence of a significant fraction of electrochemically inactive carbon contributes to the underestimation of the intrinsic gravimetric capacity of the active phase when calculated on the total composite mass [32]. Therefore, a trade-off between improved electronical performances and energy density should be set. Raman spectrum in Fig. 1d reveals the two typical bands of carbon, D- and G-bands, located at 1347 cm^{-1} and 1582 cm^{-1} , respectively. The intensity ratio $I_{\text{D}}/I_{\text{G}}$ is calculated to be 1.01 reflecting the presence of disorder and defects in the sp^2 -carbon framework [33]. Interestingly, the vibrational modes of $(\text{PO}_4)^{3-}$ group typically in the range 400–1100 cm^{-1} are not visible, denoting that carbon may be covering the surface of cathodic material absorbing the incoming laser radiation, thus reducing the Raman effect coming from the bulk of the material. Nonetheless, further insights of the $\text{Na}_{3.4}\text{Mn}_{1.2}\text{Ti}_{0.8}(\text{PO}_4)_3$ phase can be obtained by promoting the partial ablation of the carbon coating through an increase in the laser power. As shown in Fig. S2, the ablated sample exhibits several bands compared to the non-ablated composite $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP/C}$ in the 200–1100 cm^{-1} region. In details, the band at around 917 cm^{-1} can be attributed to the A_g mode of symmetric stretching of phosphate groups.

The bands centered at around 663 cm^{-1} and 558 cm^{-1} can be ascribed to asymmetric and symmetric bending modes of PO_4 tetrahedra, associated with B_{2g} and A_{2g} symmetries, respectively. The peak located at 458 cm^{-1} can be attributed to sodium cage modes with translating Na^+ and breathing cage surrounded by O^{2-} ions [34,35]. Finally, the features observed in the region below 400 cm^{-1} can be attributed to the bending modes of Mn-O and Ti-O framework [19,35].

Morphological features and mapping of the elements were characterized by SEM-EDX analysis as shown in Fig. 2. The $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP/C}$ material shows an irregular particle shape in the micrometer range (Fig. 2a,b) [13,26] with elements uniformly distributed in the sample (Fig. 2d-h). To assess the elemental composition, accurate stoichiometric ratio of Na and Mn were determined with ICP-OES analysis, while the determination of Ti has not been conducted with this technique since Ti^{4+} hardly dissolves in conventional mineral acids, instead requiring the harmful hydrofluoric acid, [36] which must be avoided. Nevertheless, titanium content may be estimated from the Mn:Ti ratio obtained by EDX analysis. As reported in Table S2, the obtained ratio Na:Mn with ICP-OES is 2.85, which is very close to the theoretical value 2.83. On the other hand, EDX analysis reveals that the experimental atomic ratio Mn:Ti is 1.48 (see Table S3), which is well consistent with the theoretical ratio (1.50). All these results confirm that the expected stoichiometry has been obtained.

3.2. Electrochemical characterization

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) was performed during the first three cycles to assess the redox reactions occurring in $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP/C}$ electrode. As shown in Fig. 3a, anodic and cathodic scans of $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP/C}$ reveal three pairs of peaks located at 2.23/2.18 V, 3.50/3.35 V and 4.08/3.95 V belonging to $\text{Ti}^{4+}/\text{Ti}^{3+}$, $\text{Mn}^{3+}/\text{Mn}^{2+}$ and $\text{Mn}^{4+}/\text{Mn}^{3+}$ redox couples, respectively. After the first cycle, a strong overlapping between CV curves of 2nd and 3rd cycles demonstrates the stabilization and reversibility of the electrochemical processes. The long-term cycling stability of $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP/C}$ were evaluated through galvanostatic cycling in the same potential range applying a current of 500 mA g^{-1} after 5 cycles of activation at 30 mA g^{-1} (Fig. 3b). Regarding the coulombic efficiency %, for the sake of clarity, for cathode materials it is calculated as the ratio between discharge and charge capacity in the same cycle ($\text{CE} = Q_{\text{discharge}}/Q_{\text{charge}}$) [37]. Thus, the initial coulombic efficiency % is for $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP/C}$ equal to 150.9 %. The apparently anomalous high ICE can be rationalized by considering the asymmetric activation of redox couples during the first cycle, clearly visible in Fig. 3a, where the $\text{Ti}^{4+}/\text{Ti}^{3+}$ redox couple is not accessible during the first charge process as Ti is initially present in the +4 oxidation state. Consequently, the capacity in the first charge is given by the Na^+ extraction associated with Mn redox couples. During the subsequent discharge, the Ti^{4+} is electrochemically reduced at low potential, thereby contributing to additional capacity that was not accessible in the preceding charge step. This results in a discharge capacity exceeding the charge capacity, leading to an ICE greater than 100 %. However, an “electrode-centric” definition of ICE is sometimes applied to this kind of materials, reporting ICE values < 100 %, as a result of the ratio between charge and discharge processes. This definition highlights the inability of this family of compounds ($\text{Na}_{3+2x}\text{Mn}_{1+x}\text{Ti}_{1-x}(\text{PO}_4)_3$) to exploit the oxidation of titanium in the first charge process, which is then reduced during the following discharge. Nonetheless, the $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP/C}$ materials herein synthesized, after the activation cycles, maintain the CE at values higher than 99.2 %, confirming the high reversibility of the charge/discharge processes. Regarding the specific capacity, the $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP/C}$ electrode can deliver a charge specific capacity of 119.8 mAh g^{-1} when cycled at 30 mA g^{-1} . This value is far from the theoretical value of 172.0 mAh g^{-1} calculated considering a fully three-electron redox reaction. However, if the mass of carbon in the $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP/C}$ composite is subtracted, the $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP}$ active phase extracts around 2.70 Na^+ ions per formula units. The small deviations encountered can be found in the incomplete activation of the

Fig. 2. SEM images of $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP/C}$ at magnifications of a) 500 x and b) at 627 x; c) EDX spectrum; Elemental mapping of d) Sodium; e) Manganese; f) Titanium; g) Phosphorous and h) Oxygen.

three redox couples, especially those of manganese [18]. When the current is boosted to 500 mA g^{-1} , the specific capacity moves to around 78.0 mAh g^{-1} mostly due to the higher cell polarization. However, the cell retains 94.7 % of its capacity after 100 cycles, 77.8 % after 500 cycles and 66.4 % after 1000 cycles. The effect of cell polarization is more visible from rate capability test, where the current was varied from 50 mA g^{-1} to 2000 mA g^{-1} (Fig. 3e). In particular, as can be seen in the galvanostatic profiles depicted in Fig. 3c, the plateaus become less pronounced as well as they move up during desodiation and down during sodiation, not allowing the fully exploitation of the redox centers before the cell reaches the high and low cut-off voltage values. The differential analysis of cycles $dQ dV^{-1}$ vs E_{we} clearly evidences this trend, where the peaks marked as A, B and C during oxidation and A', B' and C' during reduction shift toward higher and lower voltages, respectively, as well as they decrease in height (Fig. 3d). Especially the peak C seems to overcome the cut-off voltage, thus practically inactivating the $\text{Mn}^{4+}/\text{Mn}^{3+}$ redox couple. Similar situation happens during reduction where the cell reaches the cut-off voltage of 1.5 V shortening the $\text{Ti}^{4+}/\text{Ti}^{3+}$ redox process. Overall, the $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP/C}$ electrode shows satisfactory rate capability performances, experiencing low-capacity fade when the current is boosted. The average charge capacities are 100.5, 90.5, 77.7, 65.8, 48.6 and 29.2 mA h g^{-1} at 50, 100, 250, 1000, and 2000 mA g^{-1} , respectively. Restoring the current to 100 mA g^{-1} for up to 100 overall cycles yields a recovered specific capacity above 82.0 mA h g^{-1} after 100 cycles, highlighting the reversibility of the charge/discharge processes.

The sodium storage mechanism as well as the kinetics of Na^+ diffusion in the $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP/C}$ cathode material were investigated by CVs performed at different scan rates in the same potential window $1.5 < E_{we} < 4.2 \text{ V}$ vs Na^+/Na . To minimize the above-mentioned effect of the polarization, the scan rates applied were relatively low, being in the range 0.10 and 0.30 mV s^{-1} . As shown in Fig. 4a, the effect of polarization is remarkable only for the peak couple B/B', involving the transition between Mn^{2+} and Mn^{3+} . Indeed, the oxidation of Mn^{2+} produces the Jahn-Teller distortion active Mn^{3+} species, which is known to promote the distortion of the octahedra and sometimes increasing the overpotential [38]. Overall, the current produced by the $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP/C}$ electrode increases with the scan rate, highlighting the role of the pseudocapacitive charge storage fraction given by the electric double-layer in determining the current at higher scan rate. To investigate the prominent nature of the redox processes involved in the sodium storage mechanism, $\log i_p$ vs $\log \nu$ has been plotted in Fig. 4b,c. The linear fit allows to exploit the power-law relationship, written in the Equation (1), to estimate the faradaic and capacitive contributions:

$$i = a\nu^b \quad (1)$$

where i is the current, ν the scan rate and a and b are dimensionless parameters. As a rule of thumb, when $b = 0.5$ the process is purely faradaic and controlled by solid-state diffusion, while when $b = 1$ the process is purely capacitive. Intermediate values are commonly assigned to concurrent processes, i.e. redox pseudocapacitive process such as the near-surface adsorption of ionic species concurrent with a faradaic process [39]. The obtained b values for redox couples are highly coherent between charge and discharge. The peaks related to Ti redox processes mimic a capacitive behavior, which is typical of pseudocapacitive charge storage with a high reaction kinetics and almost no diffusion limits, while the peaks related to Mn experience a coexistence of faradaic and non-faradaic mechanisms [14]. To further study the kinetics of the redox processes, the calculation of the apparent diffusion coefficient (D_{CV}) for both cathodic and anodic peaks was performed using the Randles-Sevcik Equation (Eq. (2)):

$$i_p = (2.69 \times 10^5) AD^{1/2} C \eta^{3/2} \nu^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

where i_p (mA) is the peak current, A (cm^2) is the electrode surface area, D ($\text{cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) is the diffusion coefficient, C (mol cm^{-3}) is the concentration of Na ions in bulk, η is the number of electrons involved in the redox reaction, and ν (mV s^{-1}) is the applied scan rate [9]. To calculate D , the peaks current values i_p were plotted as a function of $\nu^{1/2}$ for charge (Fig. 4d) and discharge (Fig. 4e). All the linear fits have a R^2 -factor above 0.99. The calculated D_{CV} are in the range $5.0\text{--}0.5 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Fig. 4f), where a more sluggish kinetics is encountered for manganese redox reactions.

A further estimation of the diffusion coefficient has been carried out by applying the galvanostatic intermittent titration technique (GITT), since it ensures the near-equilibrium condition and thus minimizes overpotential and capacitive effects-induced distortions. Before the measurement, the cell was conditioned through 5 charge/discharge cycles at 30 mA g^{-1} . For each GITT step (Fig. S2a), a current pulse of 10 mA g^{-1} for 0.5 h followed by a relaxation of 2 h to reach the quasi-equilibrium voltage ($dE dt^{-1} \rightarrow 0$) has been applied until cut-off voltages are reached. The desodiation and sodiation voltage profiles during titration as a function of time are shown in Fig. 5a. The overall potential evolution mimics the typical Mn-based NASICONs profiles. Superimposed on these, the periodic potential jumps caused by the current pulses are visible, followed by relaxation segments from which quasi-equilibrium potentials (E_0) are extracted (Fig. S3a). The trend of E_0 during charge (green) and discharge (light blue) vs exchanged sodium

Fig. 3. Electrochemical characterization of $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{P/C}$ in half-cell: a) CV at 0.10 mV s^{-1} ; b) Long cycling at 500 mA g^{-1} ; c) Galvanostatic profiles at different current rates d) dQ/dE vs E_{we} curves at different current rates; e) Rate capability.

degree in $\text{Na}_{3.4-x}\text{Mn}_{1.2}\text{Ti}_{0.8}(\text{PO}_4)_3$ reveals a reversible titration extended up to $x = 2.10$ for $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{P/C}$ (Fig. 5b). The gap between the extracted Na^+ and the theoretical one can be related to the incomplete utilization of Mn redox processes, especially that associated with the high-voltage $\text{Mn}^{4+}/\text{Mn}^{3+}$ couple. Moreover, the observed voltage hysteresis observed in the equilibrium potentials cannot be solely explained by kinetic polarization, since the near-equilibrium conditions probed by GITT minimize the related effects. Hence, the persistence of voltage

hysteresis suggests the presence of other limitations governing the Na^+ storage mechanism. In this context, the IASD effect could play a pivotal role. Indeed, the partial occupation of Na^+ sites by Mn^{2+} during synthesis leads to cation disorder within the NASICON framework, practically blocking the Na^+ diffusion pathways and limiting the full utilization of Mn redox centers, being some Na^+ trapped into the structure [20,22]. This phenomenon together with the variation of P-O-Mn bond as a consequence of Mn dislocation determine the typical

Fig. 4. Electrochemical characterization of $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP}/\text{C}$ in half-cell: a) CV curves at different scan rates; Linear relationship between $\log i_p$ and $\log v$ for b) charge and c) discharge; Linear relationship between peak current (i_p) and square root of the scan rate ($v^{1/2}$) for d) charge and e) discharge; f) Trend of estimated diffusion coefficient from CV (D_{CV}) at various peaks current.

Mn-based NASICON voltage hysteresis between charge and discharge curves and incomplete Na^+ utilization [18,40.]

The Na^+ diffusion coefficients D_{GITT} ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$) have been obtained from GITT data applying Weppner-Huggins equation (Eq. (3)): [41]

$$D_{\text{GITT}} = \frac{4}{\pi} \left[\frac{I_0 V_M}{AF} \frac{dE/dx}{dE/dt^{1/2}} \right]^2, t \ll \tau \quad (3)$$

where I_0 (A) is the applied current, V_M is the $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP}$ molar volume ($154.02 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$), A is the electrode area (0.636 cm^2), F is the Faraday constant ($96,485 \text{ C mol}^{-1}$), and τ is the diffusion time (s). dE/dx is determined by derivation of the titration curves in Fig. 5b while $dE/dt^{1/2}$ is obtained from linear fit of E vs. $t^{1/2}$ at each current pulse. An example is provided for current pulse at $x = 1.01$ in $\text{Na}_{3.4-x}\text{Mn}_{1.2}\text{Ti}_{0.8}(\text{PO}_4)_3$ in Supporting Information (Fig. S3b). Fig. 5c displays the D_{GITT} values extracted as a function of x in $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP}$ while Fig. 5d displays D_{GITT} as a function of the potential. During both charge and discharge D_{GITT} remains in the range of $\sim 10^{-10}$ and $10^{-11} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ over most of the composition window, indicating a stable Na^+ transport throughout the whole cycle. Small localized maxima can be found around $\text{Ti}^{4+}/\text{Ti}^{3+}$ and $\text{Mn}^{3+}/\text{Mn}^{2+}$ redox reactions, respectively. Finally, near the highest degree of desodiation ($x \rightarrow 2.1$), a marked decrease in D_{GITT} is observed, reflecting the growing structural resistance associated with deep Na removal. Compared to the apparent diffusion coefficient obtained with CV (D_{CV}), the discrepancy obtained for peak couple B/B' ($\text{Mn}^{3+}/\text{Mn}^{2+}$) and C/C' ($\text{Mn}^{4+}/\text{Mn}^{3+}$) indicate a sluggish kinetic around the Mn redox centers, which can in turn ascribed to the locally hindered Na^+ transport

around IASD-affected domains. Moreover, the two-phase reaction mechanism involved in the Mn redox reactions [42] produce larger polarization compared to the solid-solution mechanism involved in Ti redox reaction, [19] whose effects sum up to classical CV overpotentials, hence apparently lowering the apparent diffusion coefficient D_{CV} , especially around the Mn redox processes. On the other hand, GITT measurements minimize polarization losses, probing the fast solid-state Na^+ transport in the $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP}$ lattice. Therefore, the different diffusion coefficients obtained from CV and GITT should not be considered contradictory, but rather indicative of the distinct kinetic regimes probed by the two techniques.

Further investigations of sodium-ion kinetics and interfacial behavior have been provided using EIS at various SoC values, corresponding to different Na contents during sodiation and desodiation. For these measurements, an ECC-Std cell equipped with Na-reference ring has been used. The EIS were recorded at 10th cycle in order to minimize any bias coming from activation of the material and stabilization of the interphases [34]. The obtained Nyquist dispersions collected at different voltages during desodiation (charge) and sodiation (discharge) are shown in Fig. S4a,b. At first glance, the Nyquist plots appear similar across different voltages, featuring an intercept with the real axis in the high-frequency region and two overlapped and depressed semicircles in the high-to-medium-frequency region. However, in low-frequency region, the slope of the tail which accounts for solid-state diffusion within NASICON framework changes at different SoC levels. A slope around 45°, signature of a quasi-semi-infinite behavior, is shown at

Fig. 5. Electrochemical characterization of NM_{1.2}TP/C in half-cell: a) GITT curves evolution during charge and discharge as a function of time; b) Equilibrium potential E_0 as a function of x in $Na_{3.4-x}Mn_{1.2}Ti_{0.8}(PO_4)_3$; Trend of diffusion coefficient from GITT (D_{GITT}) as a function of c) x in $Na_{3.4-x}Mn_{1.2}Ti_{0.8}(PO_4)_3$ and d) E_{we} potential vs Na⁺/Na.

intermediate potentials, while a nearly vertical line, describing reflective boundary conditions, is approached at potentials close to high and low cut-off voltages [43]. To improve the accuracy of kinetic analysis and split electrochemical processes occurring over distinct time scales, EIS spectra were deconvoluted calculating the DRT functions. The ill-posed nature of the transformation was addressed through the use of Tikhonov regularization [44]. Prior to the regularization, raw EIS data were pre-processed subtracting the low-frequency diffusion-related line in order to satisfy the boundary condition of convergence of the impedance toward the real axis when ω tends to 0, which is instead not guaranteed with the divergent low-frequency, diffusion-related Warburg impedance [33]. Hence, the raw spectra have been modeled, as a first approximation, to the equivalent circuit $R_{el}(R_{cont}C_{conv})(R_{ct}C_{dl})WC_i$, with particular attention to the fitting of the low-frequency region. In this model, R_{el} describes the Na⁺ migration through the electrolyte, estimated by the intercept with the real axis, while the series of two (RC) parallels model the two overlapped semicircles which can be ascribed to the contact resistance between electrode particles and current collectors and the charge transfer process, respectively. Finally, the WC_i elements model the low frequency line associated with solid-state diffusion. The subtraction of WC_i components results in the Nyquist dispersions shown in Fig. 6a,c. The continuous lines represent the nonlinear least squares (NLLS) fitting performed with Relaxis3 software, while the robustness of the fitting procedure is guaranteed by χ^2 values reported in Table S4a,b. For the fitting, the capacitive elements were replaced by constant phase

element (Q) to take into account any electrode surface roughness and inhomogeneity [3,39]. The Nyquist plots obtained by WC_i subtraction shown in Fig. 6a,c reveal that the high-frequency intercept on the real axis remains nearly constant across all potential steps, confirming that the resistance of the electrolyte is independent of the state of charge. On the other hand, the diameter of the overlapped semicircles shows a moderate but systematic dependence on potential: lower impedance is observed in the Mn-voltage range, while slightly larger impedance is measured going progressively down from Ti-voltage range to the lower cut-off. Overall, the NM_{1.2}TP/C electrode exhibits stable interfacial kinetics when the electrode operates within the main active redox window, showing only minor kinetics limitations at the cut-off voltages. To deconvolute the contributions of different electrochemical processes to polarization, the DRT functions have been calculated as shown in Fig. 6b,d. The optimization of the regularization parameter λ for the DRT analyses was performed by calculating the sum of squared residuals (SSR) vs. λ , assuming a Gaussian distribution [34]. Three distinct relaxation peaks are visible, labeled as P1, P2 and P3. According to their time constants, P1 and P2 peaks are the result of the deconvolution of the high-to-medium frequency overlapped semicircles. In details, peak P1 centered slightly above $\tau = 10^{-4}$ s ($f = 10^4$ Hz) is independent on potential and can be attributed to the resistance contributions of cell contacts and electrode particles [45]. On the other hand, the main peak P2, centered around $\tau = 10^{-3}$ s ($f = 10^3$ Hz), [46] is assigned to charge-transfer reactions associated with Na⁺ insertion/extraction in the

Fig. 6. Nyquist dispersions of NM_{1,2}TP/C electrode acquired during (a) desodiation and (c) sodiation in the frequency range 50 mHz < f < 15 kHz. Calculated DRT functions during (b) desodiation and (d) sodiation where P1 denotes contact resistance (R_{cont}), P2 represent charge-transfer resistance (R_{ct}) and P3 is a residue of WC_i subtraction.

NASICON lattice (R_{ct} in the equivalent circuit). Notably, the positions of the peak P1 and P2 does not change across the entire working potential, supporting the finding that the kinetics of the electrochemical processes occurring in NM_{1,2}TP/C electrode is constant throughout the voltage window [47]. Overall, the lack of significant variations in charge-transfer resistance with SoC both exclude the charge-transfer process as one of the main contributor of the voltage hysteresis and reveals that the Mn redox activity does not affect the charge-transfer kinetics. Finally, the peak P3 at high time constant ($\tau \geq 10^{-2}$ s) corresponding to the frequency region of solid-state diffusion in the Nyquist plots, is evidenced only at low potentials, and may be attributed to a low-frequency residual response after WC_i subtraction.

To investigate the aging phenomena occurring on NM_{1,2}TP/C electrode during long cycling at 500 mA g⁻¹, EIS measurements were conducted in a T-cell configuration at $E_{we} = 2.9$ vs V Na⁺/Na each tenth cycle until 90 cycles and each hundredth cycles until 1500 cycles. The obtained Nyquist plots are shown in Fig. 7a. It should be noted that the different overall impedance values obtained with respect to those

reported in Fig. S3 and Fig. 6 are due to the different cell configurations (ECC-Std cell- vs. T-cell). Nevertheless, the intrinsic electrochemical processes of NM_{1,2}TP/C electrode and their timescale are expected to remain unchanged. To confirm this, DRT functions were calculated at some representative cycles using the same approach as before. In this case, only one semicircle is evidenced in the medium-to-high frequency region shown in Fig. 7a inset, mainly describing the charge-transfer, while the contribution of contact resistance is here negligible. Therefore, only a single (RC) parallel was included in the model, resulting in an equivalent circuit $R_{el}(R_{ct}C_{dl})WC_i$. Thus, after the subtraction of WC_i elements, the obtained DRT functions (Fig. 7b) exhibit a single distinctive peak, analogous to P2 in Fig.s 6b,d and centered around $\tau = 10^{-3}$ s, which corresponds to the relaxation time of charge transfer. More interestingly, the peak decreases its height until 200 cycles, reflecting the activation and stabilization of the electrode and electrode/electrolyte interphase, then starts to gradually shift toward slower time constant and increases its height up to 1500 cycles, indicating the slowdown and deterioration of the kinetics of the charge-transfer process as a

Fig. 7. a) Nyquist plots of $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP/C}$ electrode acquired at different cycles, $E_{\text{we}} = 2.9$ V, $15 \text{ kHz} > f > 50 \text{ mHz}$ with an inset of the magnification of semicircles at high-to-medium frequency range; b) DRT functions as some representative cycles; c) Values of R_{el} and R_{ct} upon cycling and State of Health % as a function of cycles number. (d) Warburg coefficient σ_w and SoH % values as a function of cycles number.

consequence of the ageing. In order to give a deeper insight into the phenomena contributing to the ageing of $\text{NM}_{1.2}\text{TP/C}$ electrode, the evolution of the fitted parameters R_{el} , R_{ct} (Fig. 7c) and σ_w (Fig. 7d) were plotted as a function of cycles number. A stable electrolyte resistance is encountered throughout the whole cycling. On the other side, a moderate increase in the charge-transfer resistance R_{ct} and a concurrent, more pronounced raise of the Warburg coefficient σ_w with cycle number are shown. This behavior reveals a progressive deterioration of charge-transfer kinetics and a more pronounced slowdown of Na^+ diffusion within the cathode material [48], and is consistent with the gradual and constant lowering of the State Of Health (SoH %) reported in Fig. 7c,d. These findings suggest that the capacity fade of Mn-rich NASICON cathode is only partly due to interfacial issues, while is mainly governed by the evolution of solid-state Na^+ transport, with diffusional limitations becoming increasingly dominant at advanced cycling stages. To support these findings, another fresh T-cell was submitted to long cycling at 500 mA g^{-1} and GITT measurements were performed after 5, 500 and 1000

cycles to check the changes in the D_{GITT} values. As shown in Fig. S5, the D_{GITT} values calculated during discharge decreases as a function of cycles, with values dropping by approximately one order of magnitude from cycle 5 to cycle 1000. Notably, a marked decrease in D_{GITT} is observed in the voltage regions where voltage hysteresis can be captured, i.e. between 4.0–3.5 V and 3.0–2.5 V vs Na^+/Na . This means that there is a progressive increasing of the Na^+ diffusion barrier associated with the manganese redox activity, suggesting that Mn-centered redox reactions are more sensitive to cycling-induced degradation than the Ti-centered redox couple. Importantly, considering that antisite defects in Mn-based NASICON materials are primarily generated during synthesis rather than during cycling, [18,19] it can be deduced that the observed decrease in Na^+ diffusion coefficients cannot be attributed to the formation of additional antisite defects. Instead, it can be rationalized by considering the Jahn–Teller effect of Mn^{3+} , which causes local structural distortions and lattice strain accumulation within the NASICON framework, thereby increasing the Na^+ migration energy barrier

and worsening the cycle life [14,49]. Upon prolonged cycling, the accumulation of such distortions likely evidence diffusion limitations, leading to the observed decrease of D_{GITT} especially around Mn^{3+} redox activity. Overall, the decrease in D_{GITT} correlates with the observed capacity fade, confirming that the Na^+ transport play a dominant role in long-term performance degradation of $\text{NM}_{1,2}\text{TP/C}$ material.

To further investigate the aging behavior of the electrode, ex-situ XRD analysis has been performed on both pristine and 1500 cycled-aged electrodes. As shown in Fig. 8a the XRD pattern of the cycled electrode closely matches that of the pristine one, with no evident peak shifts or additional phases observed. With respect to powder (Fig. 1a), the electrodes exhibit additional reflections peaks coming from aluminum current collectors (marked as *) as well as other unknown peaks (marked as ●) which are present only on electrode samples. These results indicate that the $\text{NM}_{1,2}\text{TP}$ long-range structure is largely preserved even after prolonged cycling. In order to assess also the role of electrode deterioration in determining the capacity fade, post-mortem analysis has been performed acquiring FE-SEM imaging of pristine (Fig. 8b-f) and 1500 cycle-aged electrode (Fig. 8g-m). Prior to cycling, the $\text{NM}_{1,2}\text{TP/C}$ electrode exhibits a relatively uniform and well-organized surface morphology, with homogeneously distributed particles. After 1500 cycles, no evident cracks or severe particle agglomeration are visible, although a light increase in surface roughness can be observed in some regions. These results suggest that the morphology of the electrode upon cycling is largely preserved (consistent with the limited worsening of R_{ct}), suggesting an outstanding tolerance of the material to cycling-induced stress and supporting the suitability of the

NASICON cathode material for long-term operation.

4. Conclusions

In summary, a comprehensive electrochemical investigation of the Mn-rich NASICON cathode $\text{Na}_{3.4}\text{Mn}_{1.2}\text{Ti}_{0.8}(\text{PO}_4)_3$ has been presented, focusing the attention on sodium-ion transport, reaction kinetics and long-term aging behavior. The synthesized material crystallizes in a rhombohedral NASICON structure with a 22.4 % of carbon coating coming from the decomposition of the citric acid chelating agent, which is beneficial for the inter-particle conductivity and overall electrochemical performances. The $\text{NM}_{1,2}\text{TP/C}$ electrodes exhibit high specific capacity and relevant capacity retention over extended cycling. The rate capability test emphasizes the impact of cell polarization at high current rates, where overpotentials shift the redox reactions beyond the operating voltage window, practically limiting the contribution of the high- and low-potential redox processes, especially that of $\text{Mn}^{4+/3+}$ redox couple. GITT analysis performed under near-equilibrium conditions reveals that only $\sim 2.1 \text{ Na}^+$ can be reversibly extracted/inserted per formula unit. The persistence of a reduced Na^+ exchange and the presence of voltage hysteresis in the equilibrium potentials derived from GITT steps suggests that these effects cannot be ascribed only to kinetic polarization, but rather originate from intrinsic structural factors, such as the cation mixing related IASD and phase transformations during Na^+ insertion/extraction. Regarding the ageing mechanisms, combining the absence of detectable structural and morphological changes and the limited increase in charge-transfer resistance observed by EIS/DRT

Fig. 8. Ex-situ analysis of pristine and 1500 cycled-aged electrodes: a) XRD patterns; FE-SEM images at different magnifications for b-f) pristine and g-m) cycled $\text{NM}_{1,2}\text{TP/C}$ electrodes.

analysis, the observed increase in Warburg coefficient σ_w coupled with the decrease of D_{GIT} indicate that the capacity fade is predominantly driven by a gradual slowdown of solid-state Na^+ transport rather than by interfacial degradation or structural collapse. This behavior may be largely attributed to the Jahn–Teller activity of Mn^{3+} , which induces local lattice distortions and progressively increase the Na^+ migration energy barrier upon cycling.

Overall, this work clarifies the interplay between mass- and charge-transfer limitations and aging phenomena in Mn-rich NASICON cathodes, providing valuable guidelines for the rational design of durable and high-performance sodium-ion battery materials.

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge the financial support from “Green Electrolyte and Biomass-derived Electrodes for Sustainable Electrochemical Storage Devices (GENESIS)”, funded by Ministero dell’Università e della Ricerca, within the PRIN 2022 program (DD 104 02.02.2022) and European Union’s EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Europe Horizon (Grant Agreement N° 101,120,311).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

L. Bottoni: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **M. Arslan:** Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **L. Minnetti:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **F. Lischio:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **S. Pacetti:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **M. Piechocki:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **F. Nobili:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Francesco Nobili reports financial support was provided by Ministero dell’Università e della Ricerca. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.electacta.2026.149011](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2026.149011).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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